

Structural organization of Thoracic and Abdominal Appendages in the Giant Freshwater Prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*

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ABSTRACT

The current research clarifies the finer structural arrangement and functional importance of the appendicular system of *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* (*M. rosenbergii*), the giant freshwater prawn, by use of microscopic observation of thoracic and abdominal appendage. To examine segmentation, articulation, musculature, setation, the adult specimens were dissected and examined using the stereo and compound microscopes. The three thoracic maxillipeds had elaborate sensory and manipulative adaptations that provided coordination of feeding. Specialization of the five pereopods was progressive with anterior chelate limbs to fine manipulation and hypertrophic second pereopods to defense and prey capture as well as sexual display. The posterior walking legs had strengthened musculature that was appropriate to the benthic locomotion and posture stability. Abdominal pleopods were biramous with rhythmic articulation, which was useful in propulsion, respiration, and reproduction and uropods were hydrodynamic lamellae that worked together with the telson in quick responses to escape. Cheliped size and modification of pleopod were distinct sexual dimorphism. These appendages have a morphology that is integrated, which indicates ecological performance is evolutionary optimization between biomechanical design and ecological performance. The results demonstrate the efficiency of operational, behavioral and adaptive capabilities of *M. rosenbergii* in freshwater by segmental differentiation to offer important information on crustacean functional morphology and biomimetic biotechnological use.

Keywords: *M. rosenbergii*, Thoracic and abdominal appendages, Locomotion, Reproduction

INTRODUCTION

M. rosenbergii (*M. rosenbergii*) (De Man, 1879), most often referred to as the giant river prawn, has an exceptionally specialized and functionally diversified appendicular architecture, based on which it can be seen as ecologically versatile and economically significant in global aquaculture.

The appendages that follow the cephalic part, thoracic (pereopods) and abdominal (pleopods, uropods and telson) forms exhibit striking morphological and physiological differentiation which assembles locomotion, feeding, grooming, reproduction and environmental interactions (Iketani *et al.*, 2010).

This evolutionary perfection of crustacean differentiation of the limbs, manifesting as systematic arrangement of these appendages and their interdependence in operation, is indicative of a high level of morphological specialization, as it appears in the morphology of decapods (Panganiban *et al.*, 1995). The pereopods, which are thoracic in origin, replace the feeding-based apparatus of the cephalothorax with locomotive and manipulative apparatus of the body, and *M. rosenbergii* has five pairs of pereopods of which the first two pairs are chelate and morphologically adapted to the grip and defense, and the remaining three pairs are primarily used in locomotion (Perumal *et al.*, 2015). The former pereopods are delicate, touch sensitive, and usually applied in tender manipulation of food objects, and the latter (usually enlarged and sexually dimorphic) are the major chelae. These huge extensions are vital in not only capturing prey and combating as a method of territory but also sexual display and mate recognition (Warinthip Vetkama *et al.*, 2025). These chelipeds have musculature and exoskeletal support which is tailored to produce a lot of mechanical leverage to allow effective crushing or tearing of the substrates, which further increases feeding productivity (Warinthip Vetkama *et al.*, 2025). In addition to mechanical functioning, in recent research it has been found that cheliped movements have been involved in chemical signaling and have a suggested integrated contribution to sensory ecology (Thiraphon Deethaisong *et al.*, 2025). The locomotory pereopods (3 to 5 pairs) are sturdy structured and the coxal and meral articulations are fully developed to allow the locomotor pereopods to execute strong but highly controlled walking movements over complex benthic substrates. Detection of the substrate and hydrodynamic stability during locomotion is made possible by their distribution of setae and cuticular sensilla (Li *et al.*, 2025). These coordination mechanisms are facilitated by the segmental neuromuscular control mechanisms that coordinate propulsive, postural, and defensive reactions. The morphological distinction of the distal podomeres in the limb series is indicative of functional specialization in gripping, walking or substrate probing. Besides being involved in the benthic movement, the

appendages are also involved in burrowing as well as grooming and they also ensure the maintenance of respiratory efficiency, which is achieved by cleaning the surfaces of gills and scales of the antennal (Bauer, 1989; Bauer, 2004). The abdominal appendages or pleopods, which are situated posterolateral to the thorax, have a dual function of reproductive and locomotor. Generally, *M. rosenbergii* has five biramous pleopods with each having an exopod and endopod attached to a base protopod (Ra'anan & Cohen, 1985). In women the structures are highly evolved into ovigerous structures to ensure the egg attachment and aeration which are vital in the embryonic development (Ling, 1969; Bauer, 2004). Pleopodal setation plan and oscillating beating sequence also help in the circulation of water throughout the egg mass thereby providing sufficient oxygen (Short, 2000). Males frequently exhibit an endopod morphology in the form of gonopods that assist in the transfer of spermatophores during copulation, which is an extreme level of sexual dimorphism of the limbs and sex physiology (Sagi *et al.*, 1988; Ra'anan *et al.*, 1991). Pleopods also propel during swimming or escape responses, in which their synchronized movement generates anterior directed propulsion compared to the posterior propulsion of the uropods and telson during tail-flip escape responses (Tazaki & Cooke, 1979). Caudal fan is made up of terminal appendages-uropods and telson which are complex locomotor units that are considered to be more important in swift escaping of prey as well as stability in swimming (Govind & Blundon, 1985; Bauer, 2004). The uropods with an inner endopod and outer exopod articulated to the sixth abdominal segment has a well-defined exoskeletal curvature and a setal fringe which increases the effective surface area to hydrodynamic propulsion (A. Barki *et al.*, 1991). Median extension of the last abdominal somite forms a fan-like structure called the telson which is connected to uropods to produce powerful posterior thrusts during the tail-flip movements which is a survival strategy essential in predator avoidance (Li *et al.*, 2025). In addition to locomotion, this caudal complex is also useful in the substrate anchorage, posture control and sediment manipulation, and its multifunctional role in the behavioral ecology of *M. rosenbergii* (Santos & Pontes, 2016). The fineness of evolutionary specialization and integration is represented in the morphological complexity of these non-cephalic appendages. The evolutionary changes in the structure among the types of appendages are directly related both to the

requirements of ecological and behavioral contexts of this species whether it is foraging and defense to reproduction and habitat occupancy (Li *et al.*, 2025). The morphological plasticity of both sexes and the sex between sexes further indicates that the environmental and hormonal signals play a role in regulating the growth and functionality of the appendage (Sagi *et al.*, 1988; Okumura *et al.*, 2007). Together, these traits do not only characterize the ecological success of the species but also provide useful information on crustacean functional morphology, biomechanics and developmental plasticity. The structural organization and operational significance of these appendages have been fully understood and can be used to interpret the evolutionary and adaptive processes that have initiated crustacean diversification, as well as in the management of aquaculture systems, morphometrical assessment, and bioinspired robotics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Adult *M. rosenbergii* (De Man, 1879) specimens were caught in controlled aquaculture tanks and put into anaesthetic ice-cold water. They were dissected with a lot of care under a stereoscopic binocular microscope (Leica MZ6) and fixed instantly in 4% buffered formaldehyde in order to analyze their morphology. The fine structural features were observed under 40 x to 400 x with a compound microscope (Olympus CX23). Observations were based on the segmentation, articulation, setation patterns, and musculature. A digital camera attachment was used to take photomicrographs in order to document them. The standard crustacean morphological nomenclature, following Holdich and Jones (1983), is used. Each of the appendages was examined in both male and female specimens in order to examine sexual dimorphism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Maxillipeds (First to Third Thoracic Appendages)

In *M. rosenbergii* the first three thoracic appendages are converted into maxillipeds which act as a vital element in the cephalothoracic feeding apparatus. These appendages have two purposes mechanical handling of food and sensory perception of environmental stimulation. All maxillipeds have the common biregular form, consisting of a multi-segmented endopodite and underdeveloped exopodite, with the connection between them being

held by the basipodite and coxopodite. The tactile and chemosensory sensitivity comes as a result of the presence of plumose, serrate, and pappose setae along the margins, which allows the food particles to be effectively handled and discriminated.

Femoral Appendage (First Thoracic Appendage):

The three maxilliped are the most delicate and diminished, being structurally modified to collect food and pass it to the mouthparts. The endopodite has a slender and multi-articulate palp that contains plumose setae that are densely distributed, and serve to produce micro-currents in order to guide suspended particles towards the buccal cavity. The exopodite is abridged, but still has a useful flagellum that helps in the creation of feeding currents. The epipodite is highly developed, and it is usually involved in osmoregulation and ventilation of the branchial chamber. This appendage has a coordinative role, which is functional between the maxillae and the following maxillipeds, keeping them in time during feeding. This is evidenced by the large number of aesthetasc-like chemosensilla that is associated with chemical sensing of food quality.

Maxilla (Thoracic Appendage) Second:

The second maxilliped has a higher structural robustness, and it is food sorting, cleaning, and manipulating. Its endopodite has five segments ischium, merus, carpus, propodus, and dactylus that constitute a functional unit in the handling of particulate food. The serrate setae on the propodus and dactylus are thickly lined, and act as a combing and scraping instrument in clearing off the food particles, and the antennal extremities. The exopodite is more advanced than that of the first maxilliped and assists in the water current control in the process of feeding. The lower segments (coxopodite and basipodite) contain highly potent flexor and extensor muscles, thus, allowing fined motions important in food manipulation. The second maxilliped is also involved in grooming behavior, keeping the sensory appendages of the insect clean of detritus and epibiotic development.

Third Thoracic Appendage (Third Maxilliped):

The third maxilliped is a transitional form of structure between the feeding and locomotory appendages since it is the longest and is the most muscular one of the three. This is quite similar to the pereopods in form and musculature, and is an indication of its

evolutionary change to a semi-locomotory posture. Endopodite is highly extended with the terminal segments creating a food capturing and transferring mechanism. The propodus and dactylus possess robust and simple and serrulate setae that allow them to work with more massive pieces of food mechanically. The exopodite is minute, but efficient, supporting the weight of balancing and orientation of the appendage during the movements. The third maxilliped has many mechanosensory bristles and chemoreceptive sensilla as well, indicating that it can also perform two tasks at once as part of its tactile exploration and food-testing gustatory senses. It serves the function of being the main pre-oral manipulator where processed food is directly transferred to the mouth and aids in substrate probing and locomotion where the animal is foraging.

Functional Integration:

The three pairs of maxillipeds of *M. rosenbergii* work together in a very coordinated sequence; the first used to channel and direct food, the second to sort and clean and the third to capture and deliver it to the mouth. This combination is indicative of a developmental morphological and functional differentiation between anterior and posterior appendages, which is indicative of an adaptive evolution of the species to an effective omnivorous food source and interaction with the environment. The fact that plumose, serrate and chemosensory setae have a rich sensory armature highlights the significance of such appendages in feeding as well as perception of the environment and behavioral regulation.

Table 1: organization and functional differentiation of thoracic and abdominal appendages in *M. rosenbergii*

Appendage Type	Segmental Origin	Pair Count	Morphological Features	Primary Functions	Distinctive Notes
Maxillipeds (1st–3rd)	Thoracic segments 1–3	3 pairs	Biramous; consist of endopodite and exopodite; flattened and adapted as mouthparts	Food handling, grooming, and directing food to the mouth	Functionally act as accessory feeding appendages; bear sensory setae
1st Pereiopods	Thoracic segment 4	1 pair	Slender chelate legs with small pincers	Food manipulation and cleaning	Often called “cleaning legs” or “grooming appendages”
2nd Pereiopods	Thoracic segment 5	1 pair	Strongly chelate and elongated; sexually dimorphic (larger in males)	Grasping, defense, courtship, and aggression	Major distinguishing feature of males; exhibits blue or orange coloration
3rd Pereiopods	Thoracic segment 6	1 pair	Simple walking legs without claws	Locomotion and substrate contact	Assist in movement on surfaces
4th Pereiopods	Thoracic segment 7	1 pair	Unchelated walking appendages	Support and forward movement	Help in balancing during walking
5th Pereiopods	Thoracic segment 8	1 pair	Terminal walking legs with brush-like setae	Cleaning of body surface and locomotion	In females, aid in egg aeration and cleaning
Pleopods (1st–5th)	Abdominal segments 1–5	5 pairs	Biramous swimmerets with endopodite and exopodite; fringed with plumose setae	Swimming, respiration, and reproduction	In males, 1st–2nd pleopods modified for spermatophore transfer; in females, for egg incubation
Uropods	Abdominal segment 6	1 pair	Broad, flattened plates forming tail fan with telson	Backward propulsion and steering	Essential for escape movements (tail-flip)
Telson	Terminal segment	Single median plate	Triangular extension between uropods	Swimming, steering, and protection of posterior end	Houses anus and completes the tail fan

1. First Pereiopod

The two anterior-most pereiopods are fine, chelate appendages that are optimized to perform fine manipulative tasks. The dactylus and propodus articulate and create a tiny claw covered by thick microsetae. When observed under microscopy, it was found that well defined flexor and extensor muscle bundles were present in the merus and carpus, which enabled them to move precisely. The cuticular surface has a thin exoskeletal layer with sporadic sensory bristles indicating high levels of touch sensitivity. The first pereiopods have functional roles in grooming and retrieval of detrital food particles. Their delicate structure and its weak articulation prove their evolutionary adjustment to their dexterity rather than mechanical power.

2. Second Pereiopod (Cheliped)

The major chelipeds are the second pereiopods, which are highly sexual dimorphs. Males have hypertrophic claws having bright orange or blue pigments, and females have smaller less calcified structures. The propodus and dactylus are swollen and heavily calcified, and constitute a strong chela with cutting edges that are serrated. Chitinous reinforcement and high density of longitudinal muscle fibers in the samples were observed under a microscope, which increased grip strength. There are canals of pores and mechanoreceptive setae on the surface. Their functions are varied and include, at times, territorial defense, prey manipulation and courtship displays. The second pereiopod is, therefore, the most specialized and multifunctional limb of *M. rosenbergii*.

Fig. ???

3. Third to Fifth Pereiopods

Third to Fifth Pereiopods The *M. rosenbergii* has the third to fifth pereiopods which are the posterior walking legs and are mainly used in locomotion, posture control, substrate anchoring and

reproduction. These three pairs are segmentationally homologous in their morphology but show fine structural and functional differentiation to suit their biomechanical roles. The appendages have each coxa, basis, ischium, merus, carpus, propodus, and terminal dactylus that make up the endopodite and exopodite is reduced or vestigial.

3. Third Pereiopods:

The third sets of pereiopods occur at the point where the anterior chelate limbs change into the hind ambulatory legs. They are comparatively lengthy and strong and adapted to the main locomotor mobility. Propodus and dactylus are thin and curved in shape that creates a subchelate arrangement which improves hold on to the substrate. This duo is important in propulsion, where it assists the anterior part of the body in benthic movement. The merus and carpus segments have a thick musculature that provides mechanical leverage to be used in generating thrust. The distribution of the fine setae is on the margins of the distal propodus and dactylus to increase the tactile feedback to the locomotion and substrate exploration. The third pereiopods are important in initiating the gait cycles to give the first lift and stride during coordinated walking patterns.

4. Fourth Pereiopods:

The fourth pair denotes the mid-axis of locomotor balance and stability. They are also a little shorter and fatter structurally than the third pair and this provides them with the extra strength to support weight and maintain posture. The coxa and basis segments possess well-developed intrinsic muscles, which hold the appendage tightly to the thoracic sternum, which leads to the maintenance of the stability of the body during walking or burrowing. The joints between merus and propodus are such that they allow multi-directional flexion, which helps them to manoeuvre across irregular surfaces. They are also pereiopods, and help to bring the body back and turned during backward motion, and are compensatory when the anterior appendages are during feeding or defense. The fourth pereiopods are functionally biomechanical stabilizers which spread the gravitational and hydrodynamic loads experienced by the benthic environments.

5. Fifth Pereiopods:

The fifth group of pereiopods is a little shorter, but mechanically and physiologically adapted. In males,

the appendage supports the genital pore (gonopore) at the coxal area indicating that they have a reproductive ability in the transfer of spermatophores. Morphologically, the dactylus is narrow and flattened, which is worked out so as to make fine anchoring movements and delicate adhesion to the substrate. The body of this two is strengthened with chitinous thickening that gives the exoskeleton rigidity that is needed during mating and grooming exercises. Besides the reproductive role, the fifth pereopods help in the maintenance of the posterior stability and help to anchor the body when maintaining a burrow or resting. They can also assist in cleaning and handling the posterior parts of the body thus assisting in grooming behavior that is crucial in ensuring exoskeletal integrity.

Functional Integration:

The third to the fifth pereopods as a coordinated group of appendicular apparatuses is very effective in securing effective substrate locomotion and posture. Their symmetrical, serially homologous structure allows rhythmic and successive gait patterns of decapod crustaceans, which allows them to move steadily even in uneven surfaces. There is an adaptive streamlining in the structural gradient between the robust third and specialized fifth pair in terms of benthic mobility, energy-efficient propulsion, and behavioral versatility. This integration highlights the evolutionary optimization of the posterior thoracic appendages to long-term benthic, mechanical stability, and reproductive success in *M. rosenbergii*.

Pleopods (First to Fifth Abdominal Appendages)

The pleopods are two-armed, flat objects that are used to swim and for reproduction. Every pleopod is composed of an endopodite and exopodite that have rows of plumose setae creating propulsion by synchronized movements. Microscopy showed that articulations were well developed with flexible intersegmental membranes and were able to oscillate rhythmically. Both the first and the second pleopods in males are adapted into gonopods to aid the transfer of spermatophore, whereas in females they bear fertilized eggs on the ventral surface. The musculature consists of parallel striated fibers which are adapted to quick contractions. These results support the idea that pleopods are important in locomotion, respiration, and reproductive success of *M. rosenbergii*.

6. Uropods

The uropods of *M. rosenbergii* are gigantic and paddle-like structures, which are placed on the sixth abdominal segment constituting a vital part of the caudal fan together with the telson. All uropods are biramous, containing a strong protopodite and two flattened rami, each containing an endopodite (inner branch) and exopodite (outer branch) rami densely covered with plumose setae. The appendages are locomotory, stabilizing and escape-behaviorally structured, and exhibit exceptional hydrodynamic earnestness.

The protopodite is the basal segment that joins the sixth abdominal somite laterally using flexible joints which are lined by smooth cuticular membranes. This articulation is very mobile, which makes the flexion of the tail less resistant to friction. It is a firm ground of the attachment of the muscles and conveys the contraction of the abdominal flexor and extensor muscles towards the rami. The main nerve and hemolymph also pass through the protopodite without a problem, and they enable the main nervous system to coordinate itself well during motor responses.

The exopodite, which is the outer lamella, is wide and a little bigger than the endopodite. It is marked by a transverse suture, the diaeresis, that splits it into proximal and distal plates giving it the ability to be flexible and efficient in displacing water. Long plumose setae cover the lateral and distal margins and expand fully during the power stroke to create as much thrust as possible and contract during the recovery stroke to create as little drag as possible. This oar-like process causes the exopodite to be the major source of backward propulsion during escape reflexes. The endopodite which is in the middle of both resembles the overall shape of the exopodite and is smaller and more or less rigid. The inside of it has plumose setae which are fine, and serve to increase surface area, and to aid in the channeling of water.

The endopodite plays a major role in stabilizing, enabling the directional movement and sustaining the lateral balance to be controlled when a fish is swimming. The stiffness of its structure gives counter-support to the pliable exopodite to allow coordinated water displacement on locomotion. Both uropods are functional partners of the telson to generate quick reverse propulsion during the tail-flip escape reaction. As the abdominal flexor muscles shrink, the telson and

uropods fold downwards beneath the abdomen to produce a strong jet of water therefore propelling the prawn backwards almost immediately. The huge surface area and setose margins facilitate water resistance during this movement so that efficient propulsion occurs with minimum expenditure of energy. Conversely, in normal swimming, the uropods assume the roles of stabilizers and rudders turning the direction and keeping the balance. The lamellar pattern and flexible articulations presents them with the ability to make small adjustments of the flow of water and control the direction and the posture in all kinds of hydrodynamic situations. The articulating membranes have a smooth lubricated texture microscopically, which reduces friction and wear during quick strokes. The cuticular surface is smooth and tough and minimizes turbulence in the area of the appendage.

Fig. ???

These morphological and material adaptations help to increase hydrodynamic efficiency of the uropods. The uropods of *M. rosenbergii* are, in general, an elegant biomechanical system that has been adapted to achieve high propulsion speed as well as accuracy. Their interaction with the telson in an organized fashion renders them useful in escaping as well as providing excellent control and stability in normal swimming; an evolutionary enhancement that is paramount to survival in dynamic aquatic environments.

DISCUSSION

The current analysis reports a comprehensive microscopic analysis of thoracic and abdominal appendiculus of *M. rosenbergii*, which indicates the complexity of ecological adaptability as well as behavioral spectrum served by structural

differentiation of these segments. The results show that the prawn example of the appendicular system is an illustration of evolutionary optimization and in such a scenario, serially homologous limbs are highly specific in their changes and as a result, can collectively increase feeding, locomotion, defense, reproduction, and survival. This morphological divergence principle based on a shared arthropod limb blueprint has been identified as a major driver to crustacean diversity; what is currently being observed goes to buttress the developmental patterns outlined by Panganiban *et al.* (1995). The maxillipeds had an increasing specialization in the form of sensitive organs to sturdy manipulative appendages. The refined organisation of the plumose and pappose setae of the first maxilliped (notably, in food filtering and current generation) is also in contrast with the more powerful serrate setae of the second maxilliped (used in scraping, sorting and cleansing). The longest and the strongest of the maxilliped uses is the third, which is the major pre-oral manipulator. This progressive degree of structural sophistication is associated with an evolutionary gradient of feeding evolution in which it is proposed that larger food objects are actively broken up by functional structures on the basis of filtration, yet this theme continues to be echoed in subsequent functional morphological analyses of decapods (Bauer, 1989, 2004). The maximumiped complement of the maxillipeds including mechanosensilla, chemoreceptive setae and aesthetic-like structures supports the importance of these actions in the evaluation of environmental patterns and in controlling feeding behaviour. These characteristics are in line with the recent discoveries that neuro-stimulants like glutamate and serotonin regulate feeding activity in *M. rosenbergii* (Thiraphon Deethaisong *et al.*, 2025), which stresses the high interrelations between morphology and sensory physiology. The earliest pereopods (delicate and well-setose) are designed to help groom and manipulate tiny-size food items. They have lowered mechanical power, but elevated sense of touch that is in line with their cleaning legs, which keep the protection of the antennal and branchial sense organs intact. The major chelipeds or the second pereopods were highly sexually dimorphic. These appendages were highly calcified, hypertrophied and densely loaded with longitudinal muscle fibers in males, which are in line with their role in aggressive interactions, prey capture, territory defense and mating displays (A. Barki *et al.*, 1991). Their serrated cutting edges and thick

mechanoreceptive setae increase forces exerted as well as environmental taste, and the recent research findings in this area confirm such a character of cheliped musculature in male animals, related to the state of agonistic behavior (Li *et al.*, 2025). The case of the chelipeds as dual in treating its prey and socializing to talk was the source of its evolutionary importance. The third, fourth and fifth pereopods showed structural gradations in line with the functions in benthic motion, support of weight and stabilization. The third pereopods are the longest and comparatively thin, which are required in the forward propulsion and engagement with the substrate. The fourth pair that are shorter and stronger are to offer support to the middle part of the body and stability when walking or burrowing. The biomechanical partitioning of locomotor functions is manifested in such morphological differentiation of the posterior three pairs, a characteristic of wide usage in decapod gait studies. The size of the fifth pereopods is smaller but had specialized morphological characteristics of the reproductive functioning, especially among males, in which the gonopores are found on the coxae. These are used in the sperm transfer during mating posture, grooming, and stability maintenance (Sagi *et al.*, 1986; Siddiqui *et al.*, 1997; Cohen *et al.*, 2009). The fact that they can reproduce and be involved in locomotion points to the adaptive plasticity of thoracic appendages. The pleopods of the abdomen all had a biramous, setose structure of those decapod swimmerets, which showed much sex difference. The pleopods in females had thick plume setae which help in the attaching of eggs and in boosting air circulation and defense. This construction provides the mass with oxygenation and ventilation and corresponds to what previous assessments of the motherly tending habits in *M. rosenbergii* temperamental indicated (Jérôme Murienne *et al.*, 2022). The oscillating movement of pleopods using the help of flexible articulations and striated musculature is related not only to reproductive success but also to locomotion and respiration, which is also in agreement with the previously known roles of swimmerets in decapod biology (Short, 2000). In men, alterations of the first and second pleopods into gonopods, specialized in the exact transfer of spermatophores indicates one of the most conspicuous instances of sexual dimorphism in the specimens (Sagi *et al.*, 1986; Cohen *et al.*, 2009). It is such morphological specialization that highlights the evolutionary regimes that are relevant to unify reproductive morphology. A very sophisticated caudal

fan mechanism of the uropods and telson was the resultant movement of high hydrodynamic efficacy. The uropods, with their broad-flattened rami, densely enriched with plumose setae--stretch out the useful surface area on the occasion of the tail-flip, making it possible to move backward rapidly. The described mechanism is aligned with the so-called rapid escape reflex proposed by Kuguru, (2019), during which the simultaneous contraction of the abdominal flexor muscles will cause instant displacement to predators. Both escape and routine swimming make use of the ability of the exopodite to cuvate a diaeresis which increases flexibility enabling the modulation in water displacement. The low-friction articulating membranes and smooth cuticular surfaces that can be observed under the microscope probably decrease drag and mechanical wear preventing manifest long-term dynamics. The caudal fan further assists in steering, stabilization, and posture to use in both benthic or pelagic movement just like the behavior does in the lab (Santos and Pontes, 2016). In all the types of appendages, the results are based on the interaction of morphology, behavior, and ecological adaptation. The evidences of sexual dimorphism, mostly attributed to the chelipeds and pleopods, indicate the complex social associated with the species together with mating structure. They depend not solely on the ecological pressures, but also on endocrine and developmental regulation of the limbs development and their differentiation (Ilan Karplus, 2005). Specialization of appendages is a biological source of versatility that has allowed *M. rosenbergii* to become successful in a variety of freshwater habitats, and on which the economic exploitation of this species in world aquaculture is based. The structural understanding produced in this work has more far-reaching implications with the taxonomy, management of aquaculture as well as bioinspired engineering. The knowledge of limb biomechanics can be used to inform the creation of better husbandry approaches, especially those that facilitate natural behaviors in regard to feeding, defense, and reproduction. Additionally, the mechanical principles that govern the generation of cheliped forces, the ventilatory currents of pleopods and uropodal robots could be used to provide suggestions on the development of underwater robots, micro-propulsions and adaptive locomotor technologies. In the end, the structure of the appendiculous structures of *M. rosenbergii* is an example of the build up of morphological sophistication of successively homologous limbs to

produce remarkable functional heterogeneity in the lives of the species, permitting global distribution of reproductive fitness in diverse environments.

CONCLUSION

The microscopic analysis of the *M. rosenbergii* appendages shows very high level of structural specialization due to the diversity of their operation. There is feeding and sense organism adaptation in maxillipeds, gradation of manipulation to locomotion in pereopods, and a combination of swimming and reproduction in pleopods and uropods. When all these appendages work together, they demonstrate the evolutionary perfecting of the functional morphology which is necessary in the survival, feeding efficiency, and reproduction of the decapod crustacean.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to **Prof. Dr. Rokade Pramod**

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